

1 **Supplemental Information for, “Psilocybin decreases neural responsiveness and**
2 **increases functional connectivity while preserving pure-tone frequency selectivity in**
3 **mouse auditory cortex”, in the Journal of Neurophysiology**

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26 **Supplemental Video S1 (click the image to access video). Real-time and slow-motion**
27 **video of head-twitch responses (HTRs).** Mice were videoed from above in a clear acrylic
28 box with bedding. Videos were made at 150 frames per second. To better visualize fast mouse
29 movement, videos were analyzed at 30 frames per second to facilitate manual labeling of
30 HTRs. HTRs were reliably observed and labeled after psilocybin injection.

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33 **Supplemental Video S2 (click the image to access video). Computation of behavioral**
34 **movement.** A frame differencing algorithm was used to quantify mouse movement around the
35 cage (see Methods). The video shows how pixel brightness in the frame difference video
36 indicates mouse movement.

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